

EFFECT OF SPACE ENVIRONMENT ON THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) often used in precise structures of satellite systems for examples, optical benches and high gain antennas, since their coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) can design almost zero by controlling laminate sequence. Within usage on orbit, satellite structures exposed severe thermal cycle loading between -170°C to 120°C. CTE and Young's modulus change of CFRP by thermal cycle loading were precisely investigated to understand the damage mechanism of CFRP. By thermal cycle loading Young's modulus of CFRP were degraded up to 6% from its original value, however, CTE changes of CFRP laminates by thermal cycles were slight. Damages related to the Young's modulus change were discussed by experimental observations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) often used in precise structures of satellite systems for examples, optical benches and high gain antennas, since their coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) can design almost zero by controlling laminate sequence. This is because carbon fibers have unique mechanical and thermal properties; it has a superior high stiffness and negative number of CTE in fiber axis direction, and low stiffness and positive number CTE in radius direction. On the other hand, CTE and elastic modulus of CFRPs are known to be changed by exposure to the space environments i.e., thermal cycles, ultraviolet rays and radial rays [1]. The matrix resin in CFRP changes its properties by space environment exposure and this change mainly causes property change in CFRP laminates. Recently, changes in the thermal and mechanical properties of CFRP laminate by space environment loads were reported by Goto et al. [1]. In the development study of the radio astronomy satellite ASTRO-G (development plan cancelled on 2011), the key component of ASTRO-G (Figure 1), a precise large deployable antenna reflector (10 m in diameter), encountered the difficulty to keep its shape to fulfil its science target frequency of 43 Hz during its service life (three years). CFRPs were used as radial ribs to maintain accurate shape of large antenna. Since the CFRP ribs were designed to use in bending mode, change of bending modulus and CTE of CFRP were investigated. Typical examples of bending modulus change by various environmental exposures were shown in Figure 2. In this Figure, it can be understandable that thermal cycle was the main degradation source and the

bending modulus degraded about 7% in 1.5 years (half of the designed satellite life). This modulus change has been examined only after the one specific number of cycles, so the elastic modulus and also CTE change mechanism was not understood well.

Figure 1: Images of ASTRO-G radio astronomy satellite on orbit.

Figure 2: Change in bending modulus by space environmental loads.

The thermal cycling or fatigue often damaged CFRP, and initial damages originated from transverse cracks in the CFRP laminates and those transverse cracks cause delamination to realize total fracture [2-6]. In this study, therefore, changes in Young's modulus and CTE due to thermal cycling were examined to understand damage process of CFRP on orbit. The damages by thermal cycling were also precisely observed to understand damage process.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Table 1 shows the laminate sequences and material features of CFRP laminates. Two types of matrix resin were used in the study, one was epoxy and the other was poly-cyanate resin. Specimens are denoted as EPX for epoxy matrix CFRP and PCY for poly-cyanate resin. EPX was composed by PAN-based high modulus carbon fiber (Besfite UMS45, Toho Tenax), and toughened epoxy resin as the matrix (# 133, Toho Tenax). Carbon fiber in PCY was PAN based high modulus carbon fiber (TORAYCA M46JB, Toray corporation) and the matrix was poly-cyanate resin (NM31, JX Nippon Oil and Energy corporation). The stacking sequences of both CFRP laminates was $[0/30/90/-30/0]_{4S}$. These laminates were designed to possess less than $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$ 1/K in zero degree direction. The polished cross section were shown in Figure 3.

Table 1: Properties of specimens.

Name	EPX	PCY
Fiber	PAN, UM46	PAN, M46JB
Matrix resin	Epoxy, #133	Poly-cyanate ester, NM31
Lamination configuration	[0/30/90/-30/0] _{4SYM} 40PLY	[0/30/90/-30/0] _{4SYM} 40PLY
Dimension of specimens (L×W×T) [mm]	160×1.5×3.4 (Tensile test) 10×1.5×3.4 (CTE measurement)	160×1.5×4.5 (Tensile test) 10×1.5×4.5 (CTE measurement)

Figure 3: Polished surface of the CFRP laminates (PCY).

2.2 Thermal cycle test

Thermal cycle test was carried out between -196 °C by liquid nitrogen exposure and 120 °C in air by a drying oven (DX602, Yamato-scientific). Figure 4 shows the temperature history of thermal cycle load. The specimens were kept at room temperature for 10 minutes to minimize thermal shock.

Figure 4: Thermal cycle history.

Damages in the CFRP laminates were observed by an optical microscope. Crack density were evaluated under the basis of observation results.

2.3 Tensile test

Tensile tests in 0° direction were conducted to measure Young's modulus of the CFRP laminates. Specimens were tensile tested with a screw driven testing machine (AG-X, Shimadzu Co. Ltd) and a

video based non-contact displacement sensor (TRView, Shimadzu Co. Ltd) in air at room temperature. The shape and dimensions of a tensile test specimen was shown in Figure 5. Four tabs (1 mm thick GFRP) were adhered with an epoxy resin adhesive on both ends of the specimen to protect specimen in gripping area. Two target markers for displacement measurement were adhered with the interval length of 30 mm. Specimens were polished to observe damage at the surface of the specimen. 1 μm diamond paste was used to finish polished surface. After 100 cycles, cross sections at A, B and C in Fig. 3 were observed to clarify damage process in 0° plies.

Figure 5: Shape and dimensions of specimens.

Tensile test cycled seven times, and measurement of Young's modulus was conducted from 0.2 to 0.4% strain regions in the last three loading cycles. The averaged Young's modulus in the last three loading cycle were defined as Young's modulus of the specimen. Young's modulus measurements were carried out at every 5cycles up to 20 cycles and every 10 cycles up to 50, and finally at 100 cycles. Observation of the specimen surface carried out at the same number of cycles to elucidate damage process.

2.4 CTE measurement

CTE measurements before and after thermal cycle were conducted by laser interferometry methods (LIX-1, Shinku-RIKO Corp.). The temperature range was set from -150 °C to 120 °C.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Modulus change by thermal cycle

Figure 6 shows the Young's modulus change by thermal cycles for EPX and PCY.

Figure 6: Young's modulus change of EPX and PCY

Young's modulus of both EPX and PCY degraded with number of thermal cycle. Young's modulus of all specimens decreased up to about 20 cycles and the degradation almost saturated up to 100 cycles. Young's modulus of EPX decreased about 3 % and PCY decreased 6 % in average. From the theory of lamination, 6 % degradation can not be achieved even in the assumption that the young's modulus in transverse direction of lamina becomes zero. This means that the damages induced by thermal cycles degrade the young's modulus in fiber axis direction.

3.2 damages in 90° plies

Transverse cracks shown in Figure 7 were observed in 90° ply. After thermal cycle test, transverse cracks were observed in the two 90° layers located on the most surface side. Figure 8 shows the number of crack per 1mm occurred on 90° layer located on the most surface side. Crack density of both EPX and PCY rapidly increased up to 20 cycles, and then increased slightly to 50 cycles. Crack density reached 3 cracks per 1mm crack at 100 cycles for both CFRPs.

Figure 7: Transverse cracks in 90° ply

Figure 8: Change of crack density

3.3 Damage in 0° plies

Figure 9 shows cross section of PCY after 100 cycles. Many transverse crack observed in 90° plies, however, very few transverse cracks in 0° and ±30° plies found only around the surface area of the specimen. Red line in Figure 9 shows the typical example of a delamination between 0° and 30° ply. The delamination initiates from the surface and the lengths of the delamination were about 320µm ~

400 μ m. This fact implies that this delamination would be the source of Young's modulus degradation.

Figure 9: Delamination between 30° and 90° layers of PCY

3.4 CTE change

CTE changes by thermal cycles were summarized in table2. CTE in table 2 was the averaged value through the temperature range. Crack density in 90° plies and ratio of delamination between 90° and $\pm 30^\circ$ plies are also shown in table 2. Not like Young's modulus change, CTE of EPX and PCY changed slightly in the order of 1.0×10^{-7} 1/K. CTE of EPX slightly enlarged in negative value. On the contrary, CTE of PCY shifted slightly to positive value. From the structural point of view, no CTE change by thermal cycle could be an excellent feature of this CFRP laminates to use in optical benches to keep its shape.

Table 2: CTE of specimens

Specimen	Length [mm]	Mean CTE [$\times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$]		Crack density [n/mm]		Delamination [%]	
		0cycle	20cycle	0cycle	20cycle	0cycle	20cycle
Epoxy-1	10	-0.15	-0.28	0.13	2.3	0	21
Epoxy-2	10	-0.17	-0.19	0.28	2.2	0	12
Cyanate-1	10	-0.0089	0.088	0.13	3.4	0	20
Cyanate-2	10	-0.13	-0.091	0.30	3.4	0	30

CONCLUSION

Young's modulus of CFRP laminates degraded by thermal cycle. The young's modulus degradation almost saturated at 20 cycles. On the contrary, CTE changes of CFRP laminates by thermal cycles were slight. Typical damages induced by thermal cycles were transverse cracks in 90° plies and delamination between 90° and $\pm 30^\circ$ plies. From these facts, the delamination would be a main source for the modulus degradation of CFRP laminate. In the actual usage of these CFRP laminates in precise structures in a satellite, CFRPs need to expose at least 20 thermal cycles before installation to keep same modulus during the operation on orbit.

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